

CURRENT RULES AND REGULATIONS REGARDING THE PROVISION OF PSYCHOLOGICAL SERVICES IN TURKEY

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Abstract

Psychological services in Turkey are of utmost importance in the effective management of mental health issues and in assisting people in navigating the complexities of contemporary society. The responsibility for overseeing psychological services at educational institutions is within the purview of the Ministry of National Education, with the task of delivering advice services being entrusted to school counselors. The legal framework delineates the responsibilities associated with these occupations, including the delivery of developmental and preventative interventions, therapeutic interventions, and supportive interventions. The Ministry further aids with the implementation and integration of student progress reports, with the active participation of school counselors. Nevertheless, the existing legislation fails to provide a comprehensive delineation of the specific duties and obligations that are given to K-12 school counselors. Yildirim and Şahin (2021) argue that the efficacy of consultant positions is impeded by the absence of stringent training criteria and clearly defined limitations on the use of the job designation "Consultant" in job descriptions. The lack of explicit regulation pertaining to employment titles permits the use of the term "Counselor" in job descriptions, hence posing challenges for professionals operating within the domain of psychiatric services in Turkey. In brief, the regulations and guidelines pertaining to psychological services established by the Ministry of National Education in Turkey exhibit a dearth of precision in delineating the specific responsibilities and duties of K-12 school counselors. Professionals

residing in the area have challenges in obtaining recognition for their professional designations and the significance of their contributions. As per the findings of Aydin and Karaman (2021), the Ministry of National Education in Turkey assumes the role of overseeing and administering psychological services. Within this framework, educational establishments assume a significant role in delineating the responsibilities and commitments of school psychologists. Nevertheless, there exists a dearth of lucidity pertaining to the precise responsibilities and functions of school counselors throughout different tiers of education.

Keywords: *Psychological Services in Turkey, Provision of Psychological Services, Psychological Services and Current Rules and Regulations in Turkey, Psychological Science in Turkey, Psychological Services*

Introduction

Despite the enactment of specific laws, disparities in the perception of school counselors continue to endure, since some educators and administrators see them as privileged persons with a reduced workload. This viewpoint diminishes the significance and efficacy of school counselors, perhaps impeding their ability to fulfill their responsibilities with proficiency. In Turkey, professionals engaged in the provision of psychological services are subject to certain limitations and regulatory processes pertaining to licensure. Bařtemur and Uçar (2022) argue that the absence of a clearly defined legal framework for licensing poses challenges in ensuring that persons possess the requisite competences and knowledge. The lack of a unified curriculum, regulatory framework, or accrediting system for counseling programs in Turkey has resulted in significant variations in terms of both content and professional training. However, there is a need for more explicit criteria pertaining to the precise responsibilities and commitments of K-12 educational counselors. To adequately address these difficulties, it is crucial to broaden the pool of specialists inside educational institutions by including persons who possess specialized knowledge in educational psychology, school psychology, and school social work. These specialists provide a more extensive array of specialized services and support that beyond the conventional duties of school counselors. The importance of certification and the advocacy for standardized consultant programs cannot be disregarded. Nevertheless, the establishment of clear and unambiguous criteria for delineating the specific duties and responsibilities of school counselors, as well as the creation of structured and formally acknowledged counseling initiatives, continue to provide persistent challenges.

25 Methodology Despite the presence of legislative measures, there persist some difficulties, particularly the constrained accessibility of mental health specialists inside educational establishments. The primary objective of the commission is to provide a uniform curriculum, regulatory framework, and accreditation mechanism for consultant programs in Turkey. Kalkan and Can (2019) assert that the Ministry of National Education offers a clear delineation of the duties associated with these services. Nevertheless, the lack of a universally adopted curriculum, regulatory structure, or accrediting system for guiding programs results in notable discrepancies in both education and training. Arslan and Sommers-Flanagan (2018) assert that the primary objective of the Professional Association Commission is to formulate and implement a standardized vocational education system within a certain domain. Additionally, its objective is to foster professional acknowledgment and expertise within the field of counseling. The understanding and delineation of the roles and jurisdiction of school psychologists is essential to mitigate ambiguity and maximize the efficient use of their skills in addressing the psychological requirements of children. Saputro et al. (2022) assert that the consulting sector has challenges when it comes to the implementation of consistent standards, certification processes, and the delineation of roles and responsibilities.

Literature Review

The Turkish Psychological Guidance and Counseling Association (TPGCA) is now facing challenges stemming from a dearth of adequate autonomy in the organization and management of psychological counselor training nationwide. The formation of the Professional Association Commission was intended to enhance the quality of vocational education offered in the field of consultation. To enhance the quality of counseling services in Turkey, it is crucial for governmental agencies and professional organizations to establish a collaborative initiative focused on developing a comprehensive statewide framework for the standardization and certification of counseling programs (Arslan & Sommers-Flanagan, 2018). The efficacy and quality of career counseling and guidance services in secondary and tertiary educational institutions in Turkey have encountered a range of obstacles. Several factors contribute to the current state of counselor education programs in Turkey. One such factor is the absence of a professional certification organization for these programs. This lack of accreditation hinders the establishment of standardized quality assurance measures. Additionally, the Turkish The

establishment of a comprehensive nationwide standards and accreditation framework for counseling schools has the potential to address the prevailing issues surrounding the standardization and certification of counseling programs in Turkey. This initiative would facilitate the consistent provision of superior training for counselors, hence ensuring the delivery of high-quality services. The significance of highlighting the value of counseling and cultivating a professional identity is underscored via the provision of opportunities for counselors to engage in specific educational and training endeavors. This enables the development of competencies in several domains of counseling, including career counseling and mental health counseling among others. To assure the provision of psychological services in a way that is both of high quality and efficient, it is essential for Turkey to adhere to globally recognized standards within the discipline of psychology (Vega et al., 2022). The absence of well-defined criteria and accrediting procedures for counseling institutions in Turkey has resulted in disparities in the curriculum requirements and professional advancement opportunities for counselors. Körük and Kara (2019) argue that the presence of this gap can impede the proficiency and achievement of consultants. The growing need for counseling services in educational institutions and society in Turkey underscores the need of establishing standardized certification protocols for psychological counseling programs (Overchuk et al., 2021). This strategy aims to provide a structured and all-encompassing training regimen for counselors, enhancing their professional identity and bolstering their confidence in their abilities within the field. The implementation of standardized and restructured psychological counseling programs at both the undergraduate and graduate levels is crucial to guarantee that practitioners possess the necessary competences to effectively address the requirements of their clients. The establishment of the Professional Associations Commission in Turkey signifies a notable advancement in the enhancement and uniformity of professional education within the consulting sector of the Turkish economy. Counselor candidates in Turkey endeavor to enhance the coherence and quality of their professional training with the aim of attaining favorable outcomes. There is a growing acknowledgement of the need to establish regulated and approved consulting programs within the Turkish setting. This knowledge arises from the recognition that these programs provide thorough training for counselors and cultivate a feeling of assurance and tranquility in clients. The present research, done by Demir and Gazioğlu (2012), aims to examine the impact of regulatory measures on psychological practices within the context of Turkey. The study used a case study approach to examine the unique setting of Turkey. This study emphasizes the need of implementing standards and certification protocols to guarantee that advisers possess sufficient training and fulfill customer expectations.

Findings

Further efforts are required to develop comprehensive standards and legislation pertaining to the provision of psychiatric treatment in Turkey. In Turkey, the absence of well-defined standards and accrediting systems gives rise to disparities in the quality of education and 26 training bestowed upon consultants. The effective resolution of difficulties in Turkey and the enhancement of regulation and certification of psychological services need the collaborative efforts of many stakeholders, including professional organizations, educational institutions, and government authorities. Körük and Kara (2019) propose the establishment of a dedicated national certifying organization that would prioritize the delivery of psychological services. The organization will have the responsibility of generating and upholding standardized metrics for educational programs, setting criteria for licensure or certification, and advocating for ethical norms.

Argument

The current state of regulations and certification procedures pertaining to the delivery of psychological services in Turkey is currently in a phase of growth. Nevertheless, there is a growing acceptance of the need to establish consistency and restructure counseling programs in Turkey to foster the advancement of the field of psychology. The inception of the Professional Association Commission in 2003 was driven by the objective of mitigating issues and inadequacies pertaining to standards and certification. The Professional Association Commission, which was founded in 2003 by the Turkish Psychological Counseling and Guidance Association, assumes a crucial role in Turkey by prioritizing the advancement and organization of professional training initiatives within the realm of psychology. The primary objective of this project is to guarantee adherence of counseling programs to predetermined criteria and standards, therefore instilling trust among clients and the public in the quality of psychological services provided at a national level. The absence of uniform curriculum, regulation, and certification in guidance schools has given rise to disparities in professional training and curricula. Ongoing endeavors are being undertaken to formulate a uniform curriculum for counseling programs in Turkey, with the aim of setting benchmarks for professional training and supervision and implementing accreditation procedures to guarantee that psychological services in Turkey comply with rigorous quality criteria. The Professional

Association Commission plays a crucial role in ensuring that consultant programs in Turkey provide complete training and adhere to the requisite rules and regulations. The absence of well-defined standards and formal recognition within psychological counseling programs in Turkey has a direct influence on the development of professional identity and advancement in psychological counseling (Aydin & Karaman, 2021). To effectively address these difficulties, it is imperative to emphasize the standardization and certification of both undergraduate and graduate counseling programs. This will result in enhanced services for people, families, and communities inside educational institutions and across diverse geographical areas. The primary objective of the Professional Associations Commission, established by the Turkish Psychological Counseling and Guidance Association, is to address the issue of disparate standards and accreditation among different psychological counseling institutes. The objective is to guarantee that counseling practitioners possess the requisite training and credentials to provide sufficient and ethical therapy to their clientele. The primary objective of the Professional Association Commission is to promote the progress and harmonization of educational and training initiatives in the domains of counseling and psychology in Turkey, therefore addressing the existing issue of inconsistency throughout the nation. The existing legislation primarily focuses on enhancing and unifying vocational education, with the objective of establishing a uniform curriculum and implementing accrediting procedures. Nevertheless, the standardization and certification procedure of consultant programs in Turkey persistently encounters ongoing problems. The process includes the formulation of explicit rules for curriculum, training programs, and accreditation procedures to provide a uniform level of competence and comprehension among consulting practitioners.

Conclusion

Despite concerted efforts to create consultant services and promote standards within the Turkish context, the profession continues to encounter a multitude of problems. The problems include disparities in curriculum and training, the need for standardization and certification of consulting groups, and the matter of professional identity and specialty. The formation of the Professional Association Commission in 2003 was a significant achievement in the endeavor to promote consistency and accreditation in consultant programs within the context of Turkey. Turkey now has a dearth of well-defined norms and legislation pertaining to the delivery of psychological services. This deficiency has resulted in incongruities in curriculum and vocational training within the field. The growing popularity of psychological counseling and

guidance programs in Turkey serves as an indicator of the escalating need for counselors capable of addressing the diverse requirements of people, families, educational institutions, and society at large (Körük, 2018). Nonetheless, the consultant industry in Turkey has challenges stemming from the absence of well-defined regulations and permission documentation. The current circumstances provide challenges in establishing a professional identity within the discipline and ensuring the efficacy of existing research endeavors. There exists a pressing need to advance and solidify the current norms and rules governing the administration of mental therapies in Turkey. The current law pertaining to the provision of psychiatric services in Turkey requires prompt evaluation to expedite comprehensive change and develop uniform standards. The absence of comprehensive and defined standards, norms, and credentials for counseling programs in Turkey has resulted in variations in curriculum and vocational training. The establishment of national standards and certification for counseling programs necessitates the development of a robust collaboration 27 between the Turkish government and pertinent professional organizations. The objective of this act is to establish a framework that will guarantee adherence to established requirements for psychological counseling programs in Turkey. This would therefore streamline the implementation of standardized training for psychologists throughout the nation.

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